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SCREENING OF PHYTOCHEMICALS AND DETERMINATION OF TOTAL PHENOLIC CONTENT, ANTI-OXIDANT AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *PIPER NIGRUM* LEAVES

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ABSTRACT

The study involves two methods of methanolic extraction of the powdered leaves, which ensure all the plant components of the extracted for better results. Phytochemical analysis from the extracts was performed by using standard protocols. Total phenolic content was determined by Folin–Ciocalteu's (FC) method. The antimicrobial susceptibility of the extracts was tested against *E coli*, *Pseudomonas* and *Klebsilla sp.* using agar disc diffusion method. Antioxidant property of the plant was evaluated using DPPH Method. The plant extracts were used at varying concentrations to ensure which plant extract and concentration causes the most inhibition. Phytochemical analysis of the extract indicated the present of phenol, tannin, terpenoid(except in heat extraction method of methanol extract) and carbohydrates while protein, flavonoid, steroid were absent. The phenolic content in cold extraction of methanol extract is 360µg/ml of GAE or 0.36mg of phenolic compound and in heat extraction of methanol extract is 340µg/ml of GAE or 0.34mg of phenol compound were present. The cold extraction of methanol extract demonstrated the maximum zone of inhibition against *Pseudomonas* followed by *E. coli* and *Klebsiella sp.* In case of heat extraction of methanol extract the maximum zone of inhibition against *Pseudomonas* followed by *E.coli* and *Klebsiella sp.* were seen respectively. The plant showed a significant activity with both methods. Out of the two extracts cold extraction showed the maximum antioxidant activity (78.81% inhibition in 200µg/ml) with increase in concentration. The heat extraction method showed the maximum of 77.62% inhibition in 200µg/ml concentration which reveals the dose dependent increase in percentage of inhibitory activity.

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INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are used from prehistoric times. Black pepper is one of the most widely used spices in the world. It belongs to the family Piperaceae, in the genus of Piper and scientifically known as the *Piper nigrum*. It is a woody vine and grows in tropical region. The fruit of the black pepper is used as both spice and a medicine. Phytochemicals are not vitamins or minerals but are bioactive compound found in plant foods that work with nutrient and dietary fibers to protect against disease. [1] It contains essential oils like piperine, an ammonia derived alkaloid, as well as monoterpene sabinene, pinene, terpenene, limonene, and mercene, which give this spiciness aromatic quality. It is a rich source of essential nutrient such as manganese, iron, potassium, vitamin-C, vitamin-K and dietary fibre. It also warms up the body so it promotes sweating, which helps to rid toxins of the body and used to relieve pain, flu, cold, chills, rheumatism, fever and muscular aches. [2]. These oils can help in erasing aching muscles, chilblains, arthritis, constipations, sluggish digestion in aromatherapy. [3] It is the Trans stereoisomer of 1-piperoylpiperidine. It is also known as (E, E)-1-piperoylpiperidine and (E, E)-1-[5-(1, 3-benzodioxol-5-yl)-1-oxo-2, 4-pentadienyl] piperidine. It is responsible for pungency of black pepper. Recent medical studies have shown that it is helpful in increasing the absorption of certain vitamins, selenium and β -carotene. [4] The main objective is to study the phytochemicals, total phenolic content, antimicrobial activity and antioxidant activity of the black pepper leaves.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study area:

The study was conducted at Department of Biotechnology, Assam down town University and Central Instrumentation Facility Laboratory, Assam down town University, Assam.

Plant material:

Sample collection and identification:

The samples were collected from Bongra Pachanpara of Kamrup District of Assam in the month of February, 2017. It was plucked with hand from the plant and kept in plastic bags. The plant was identified and confirmed by plant taxonomist using standard manual.

Preparation of crude extract:

The collected leaves of *Piper nigrum* were transferred to Department of Biotechnology, Assam down town University. The leaves were washed thoroughly with distilled water, cut into thin slice with the help of knife and was steamed to remove the chlorophyll from the leaves then dried in shade condition at room temperature for 15 days. They were then powdered using pestle and mortar. The powder of the leaves were sieved and stored in air-tight plastic container for further use.

In heat extraction method, 10gm of the powdered leaves were weighed and mixed in the solvent of 70% methanol in distilled water. The mixture was then boiled in microwave for 2-3 minutes and let it cool down in room temperature. While in cold extraction method, the mixture was kept in freezer for 72 hours. The mixtures are then filtered and centrifuge in 3000rpm for 5-10 minutes.

Test for phytochemicals:

Evaluation of different phytochemical from the extract was performed by previously described standard protocols. The result reveals the presence of medicinally active constituents like tannin, phenol, terpenoid, and carbohydrates in the sample.

Total Phenolic Content Test:

Total phenolic content was estimated as gallic acidequivalents (GAE) (the standard curve equation: $y = 7.026x - 0.0191$, $r^2 = 0.999$) as described by Folin-Ciocalteu's (FC) method with modifications. An aliquot (0.7 mL) of the pepper extract solution was transferred to a glass tube; 2.5ml FC reagent (previously diluted with distilled water 1:10). After 5 min, 75% sodium carbonate (2.25 mL) was added and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 90 min. The absorbance of the mixture was measured at 725 nm. [5, 6, 7] Absorbance was then measured in spectrophotometer [8] at 725nm and compared to a GA calibration curve. Phenol content is expressed as (mg/g).

Anti-microbial test:

The anti-microbial test was performed using Agar disc diffusion method with different extract.

Test organisms and inocula preparation:

Three different isolates of bacteria were selected based on their importance in health, particularly based on their association with human diseases. The standard strains of *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) *Pseudomonas* (ATCC 27853) and *Klebsilla* sp (ATCC 700603), were collected from down town hospital, Guwahati, Assam, India. They were later transported into Biotechnology department by using nutrient agar slant and preserved at 4°C for further use. The test organisms from nutrient agar slant were then transferred to nutrient agar medium to get a pure colony at 37°C for 24hrs by using standard growth method 12-13. 3-5 pure colonies were selected and transferred into a sterile test tube containing 5 ml of bacterial culture broth and kept for overnight at 37°C.

Agar disc diffusion method:

Antibacterial test was performed by agar disc diffusion method using Muller-Hilton agar [9, 10] followed by the procedures of CLSI [11]. The compounds with potential antimicrobial properties are deposited on a sterile filter paper disc which in turn shows the principle of diffusion through agar. For all the anti-microbial tests a concentration of 1mg/ml of extracts were used. The entire tests were repeated triplicate to get better result and after overnight incubation, Zone of inhibitions was measured in mm by measuring the radius using scale.

Anti-oxidant activity test:

DPPH method was used to test the anti-oxidant activity.

DPPH Method:

The antioxidant activity of methanol and aqueous extract of the plant material was assayed according to the method described before[12] with slight modification. The test extracts were prepared with the concentration of 1000µg/ml by dissolving 20mg of the methanol or water extract and the volume was made up to 20 ml by methanol or water separately. Different concentrations of the plant extracts (50µg/ml, 100µg/ml, 150µg/ml and 200µg/ml) were taken and 2ml of methanolic DPPH solution was added followed by keeping it for incubation for a period of 30 minutes. The DPPH free radical scavenging was determined in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Systronic UV-Vis Spectrophotometre-117) by measuring absorbance at 517 nm against a blank solution by taking ascorbic acid as standard. . The percentage of inhibition was calculated using

$$\% \text{ of inhibition} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of Control} - \text{Absorbance of Sample}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

RESULT**Phytochemical analysis:**

The phytochemical characteristics of the extract of *Piper nigrum* summarized below: The result reveals the presence of medicinally active constituents like phenols, tannins, terpenoid and carbohydrates.

Table:1: Result of phytochemical screening of the leave extract.

Serial no.	Phytochemical	Result	
		Heat extraction	Cold extraction
1	Phenol	+ve	+ve
2	Steroid	-ve	-ve
3	Tannins	+ve	+ve
4	Terpenoid	-ve	+ve
5	Flavonoid	-ve	-ve
6	Carbohydrate	+ve	+ve
7	Protein	-ve	-ve

Determination of phenolic content:**Heat extract:**

Table .2.1:- Table showing phenol content in methanol extract.

Serial no.	Concentration of Gallic acid	O.D. at 725nm
1	200µg/ml	0.574
2	400µg/ml	0.631
3	600µg/ml	0.685
4	800µg/ml	0.739
5	1000µg/ml	0.819
Sample	--	0.613

From the table we can conclude that 340µg/ml or 0.34 mg of GAE of phenolic compounds is present in heat extract of methanol extraction.

Cold extract:**Table .2.2:- Table showing phenol content in methanol extract.**

Serial no.	Concentration of Gallic acid	O.D. at 725nm
1	200µg/ml	0.591
2	400µg/ml	0.646
3	600µg/ml	0.696
4	800µg/ml	0.746
5	1000µg/ml	0.809
Sample	-	0.628

From the table we can conclude that 360µg/ml or 0.36mg of GAE of phenolic compounds is present in cold extract of methanol extraction.

Antimicrobial assay:**Against *Escherichia coli*:**

- The heat and cold extraction methods of methanol extract of black pepper leaves shows effect against *E. coli* by disk diffusion methods
- The sample shows zone of inhibition against the sample of 0.04ml and 0.05ml.

Zone of inhibition against *E. coli*:**Table .3.1: Table showing zone of inhibition against *E. coli*.**

Sample (ml)	Heat extract	Cold extract
0.04	0.2 cm	0.4 cm
0.05	0.4 cm	0.5 cm

Against *Pseudomonas species*:

- The extract shows effect against *Pseudomonas sp.* by disk diffusion method.
- The sample shows zone of inhibition against the sample of 0.04ml and 0.05ml.

Zone of inhibition against *Pseudomonas*:**Table.3.2: Table showing zone of inhibition against *Pseudomonas*.**

Sample (ml)	Heat extract	Cold extract
0.04	0.6 cm	0.7 cm
0.05	0.8 cm	0.9 cm

Against *Klebsiella species*:

- The extract shows effects against *Klebsiella sp.* by disk diffusion method.
- The sample shows zone of inhibition against the sample of 0.04ml and 0.05ml.

Zone of inhibition against *Klebsiella sp.*:**Table.3.3: Table showing zone of inhibition against *Klebsiella sp.***

Sample (ml)	Heat extract	Cold extract
0.04	0 cm	0 cm
0.05	0 cm	0.1 cm

Antioxidant assay**Heat extract:****Table .4.1:- Absorbance of Antioxidant assay of heat extract by DPPH method.**

Serial no.	Concentration of sample	O.D. at 517nm	% of Inhibition	IC ₅₀
1	50µg/ml	0.416	44.56%	55.28
2	100µg/ml	0.264	64.84%	
3	150µg/ml	0.203	72.96%	
4	200µg/ml	0.168	77.62%	

Positive control = 0.751.

Figure .4.1:- Graph representing antioxidant % inhibition of heat extract.

Cold extract:

Table .4.2:- Absorbance of Antioxidant assay of cold extract by DPPH method.

Serial no.	Concentration of sample	O.D. at 517nm	% of inhibition	IC ₅₀
1	50µg/ml	0.476	42.35%	61.85
2	100µg/ml	0.257	68.88%	
3	150µg/ml	0.211	74.45%	
4	200µg/ml	0.175	78.81%	

Positive control = 0.826.

Figure.4.2:- Graph representing antioxidant % inhibition of cold extract.

DISCUSSION

The entire study was carried out by using methanol extract in two different extraction methods of leaves of *Piper nigrum*. The preliminary phytochemical screening tests for the methanol extract of *Piper nigrum* leaves (Table 1.1) revealed the presence of several bioactive compounds which could be responsible for the diverse medicinal properties of the plant. Presence of phenol, tannins, terpenoid, and carbohydrate were seen in the extract of the plant. The total phenolic content was determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu method. The phenolic content in cold extraction of methanol extract is 360µg/ml of GAE of phenolic compound (Table .2.2) and in heat extraction of methanol extract is 340µg/ml of GAE of phenol compound were present (table.2.1).

In this study leaves extracts of *Piper nigrum* was administered against the three standard strains. The cold extraction of methanol extract demonstrated the maximum zone of inhibition against *Pseudomonas* (0.7cm and 0.9cm) followed by *E. coli* (0.4cm and 0.5cm). and *Klebsiella sp.* (0cm and 0.1cm). In case of heat extraction of methanol extract the maximum zone of inhibition against *Pseudomonas* (0.6cm and 0.8cm) followed by *E.coli* (0.2cm and 0.4cm) and *Klebsiella sp.* (0cm) (Table .3.1, .3.2. and .3.3.) were seen respectively. From the study standard *Pseudomonas* strain was found to be more susceptible to cold extraction of methanol extract of *Piper nigrum*.

The plant showed a significant activity with both methods. Out of the two extracts cold extraction showed the maximum antioxidant activity (78.81% inhibition in 200µg/ml) with increase in concentration. The heat extraction method showed the maximum of 77.62% inhibition in 200µg/ml concentration which reveals the dose dependent increase in percentage of inhibitory activity.

The Inhibition concentration (IC) of heat extract is 55.28 µg/ml and cold extract is 61.28 µg/ml. The present study suggests that both the extracts could be a potential source of natural antioxidant which could be of great importance for the treatment of radical related diseases and age associated diseases.

CONCLUSION

In this study the phytochemical analysis of the *Piper nigrum* leaves reveals the presence of chemicals compounds like phenol, tannins, terpenoids and carbohydrate. The total phenolic content is more in cold extraction of methanol extract showed 360µg/ml of GAE of phenol compound.

The extract upon treating with some microbes such as *Pseudomonas* followed by *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* showed inhibition of bacterial growth. Maximum inhibition was showed by cold extraction of methanol extract against *Pseudomonas* (0.9cm). The sample showed a maximum of 78.81% of antioxidant property (200µg/ml concentration of cold extraction of methanol extract).

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